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UTILIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES AS A FACTOR INFLUENCING QUALITY SECONDARY EDUCATION IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the utilization of educational resources as a factor influencing quality secondary education in South-South, Nigeria. The study was premised on the fact that educational resources provided for secondary education are not being judiciously utilized by relevant authorities in the school system in the teaching-learning process; as they still prefer the traditional teaching method to the utilization of improvised and enhanced educational resources that will spur quality education. An appropriate review of related literature was undertaken to analyze diverse views with regard to the utilization of educational resources and quality secondary education. The paper concluded that educational resources are an integral component of the school that requires regular and prompt supervision with a bid to sustain quality in the education sector in the area under review. The paper suggested that secondary school administrators and Chief inspectors of schools should consistently and regularly supervise schools to ensure the appropriate utilization of educational resources provided by the government, owing to the fact that the judicious use of the supplied educational resources will promote quality secondary education.

KEY WORDS

Utilization, Educational Resources, Quality Secondary Education, Supervision.

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1. Introduction

Quality secondary education is that type of education that is provided in a country to students in secondary schools that would assist students to acquire improved and meaningful learning that could prepare the students to face their future with confidence and assurance that what he/she has learnt will enable them to cope in the larger society after leaving school. Most parents would prefer sending their children to privately owned schools where it is perceived that quality secondary education can be achieved. This is due to the observed school discipline, effective teaching and learning that characterized the private schools against most public schools with a reduced monitoring and regular school supervision. A majority of public schools appear to be losing quality due to lack of educational resources needed for school supervision for the purpose of ensuring that standards are maintained. Available educational resources consisting human, materials and finances can influence quality of public schools when they are at the disposal of school administrators such as school principals and school supervisors. If quality of secondary education is not sustained in the public school, it could result to a high drift of candidates to private schools. This is because parents want to have a good return for their money spent on the education of their children. This is why effort has to be made to provide quality secondary education in public secondary schools through the utilization of educational resources.

Utilization of educational resources has to be managed to avoid wastage. Kapur (2019) said that the use of human, materials and finance have to be effectively put to use in a bid to achieve quality of secondary education. It is against this backdrop that Olugbenga (2019) placed the utilization of educational resources as the responsibility of school administrators. This is because utilization of learning resources is the act of assigning available human (teaching and non-teaching), financial (money) and material (furniture) resources to effect the process of instruction and learning and be able to meet significant demand and supply of the school. This idea was supported in the study by Kolawole and Ogbiye (2020) linking utilization of educational resources to efficiency of school administration. The fact is that utilization of educational resources is very important. Appropriate use of educational resources plays a significant role in the achievement of educational objectives and set goals.

Ayodele and Ogbiye (2018) noted that achievement of educational goals may not be possible without the judicious utilization of educational resources. It points to the fact that school principals and other administrators, including supervisors and inspectors has to develop the skill and knowledge in the allocation of educational resources to meet the demand for school quality in the school system in Nigeria. A study in Ekiti by Ayodele and Ogbiye (2018) showed that the level of resource utilization by school principals was moderately effective. It gives the impression that utilization of educational resources differ from one school principal to another. In line with the above observation, Okon, Arop, Osim and Ukpung (2020) affirmed that proper use of educational resources demands that they are managed in such a way that they would last longer. This is important for school supervisors whose duty it is to ensure that provision to school are in good shape always. It is against this background this study becomes necessary in order to investigate the extent to which utilization of educational resources is a factor influencing quality secondary education in South-South, Nigeria.

Quality secondary education would lay a good foundation for tertiary education in the country when educational resources provided are adequately utilized by relevant stakeholders. But findings have shown that most teaching and learning process in the school are done using the conventional talk and chalk method of instruction, thereby jettisoning the use of educational resources with will spur learning and interest in students. In this light, the objective of the study will be to examine the extent to which utilization of educational resources as a factor of influences quality secondary education in South-South, Nigeria; employing secondary data in the process of analysis.

2. Concept of Educational Resources

Resources means a stock of supply of money, material, staff and other asserts than can be drawn on by a person or organization in order to function effectively. This definition points to the fact that the objective of resources is organizational effectiveness. In other words, improved and enhanced performance of organization is correlated with available resources. Thus, the measure of the achievement in an organization will be determined

with the used available resources. Education is a social organization made concrete by the school, which according to Turkkahraman (2015) is the top of the centers where educational institutions become concrete and active. The importance of education is seen in the fact that it gives us knowledge of the world around us and changes it into something better. Education develops in us a perspective of looking at life. It helps us build opinions and have points of view on things in life. Edogun (2015) explains the importance of education in society stating that, an educated person gets better opportunities in life and it is easier for him to become successful and realize his dreams compared to someone who is uneducated. Education can be formal and informal, and it is the fundamental responsibility to ensure citizen attains the basic education. Hence, the issue of educational resources as it affects quality secondary education will continue to receive investigation. This is because it is believed that resources are needed to drive education programme anywhere in the world.

Resource needs for education goal attainment cannot be overstressed. For instance, material resources; both the availability and quality of materials can be barriers to a quality education. Resources invested in education consist of the allocation of human, material and financial resources. Each and or all of these influences the management of the education system in a given country. There is a modest relationship between educational resources and quality secondary education. According to Nicolitti and Rabe (2012), a basic set of resources is crucial for providing students with the opportunity to learn. The extent to which resources for monitoring and evaluation of the system appears to correlate the learning opportunity students may have. Educational supervision needs all the necessary resources to operate efficiently. Kotirde and Yunos (2015) found that the process of supervision is becoming a serious problem that is yet to be properly addressed in Nigeria secondary school. They were of the view that the process of supervision in secondary school in Nigeria is of paramount to the attainment of monitoring secondary schools activities for national development and the administration of the schools entirely. The implication of the above observation points to the importance of educational resources which consists of human, material and financial resources.

Human resources for education needs consist of school administrators and teaching staff in schools. The work by Haque and Kamaluddin (2014) revealed that human resources in education are principals, their deputies, and heads of the departments, teachers, parents, and guardian and school supervisors. The core responsibilities of human resource managers in education are to manage, nurture, educate and prepare the prospective human resources of the society. The school principal was singled out as one of the most important human resources of quality education and effective school administration of basic education schools in Nigeria, in the study by Shuaibu (2016). Supervisors from the secondary education management board along school principals were identified as human resources in education in the study by Iloabuchi, Abraham and Afangideh (2016). Their study shows that teaching staff and students are to be supervised by both school principals as well as supervisors. Their study which was carried out in Abia State examined the management of teaching staff for quality education delivery in secondary education, which involved 222 principals and 118 supervisors from where a sample of 270 participants were drawn using the proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Based on the adopted descriptive survey, it was established that both school principals and officials from the education management board provide both internal and external supervision which placed them as human resources in the education sector for quality control of the school system.

Omebe (2014) examines issues and challenges of human resource management in education in Ebonyi State. According to her, human resource management is the design of formal systems in an organization to ensure effective and efficient use of human talents to accomplish organizational goals. She found that every educational system at every level depends heavily on the human resources for execution of its programme such as school supervision at the secondary schools. She also listed the functions of human resource management in education to include staff maintenance, staff relations, staff development, procurement of staff and job performance reward. The challenges facing human resource management as indicated in her finding consists of poor working condition, problem of staffing, funding, incessant transfer of teacher among others. Otu, Salawu and Ajadi (2017) shows that the teacher as one of the human resource in education is the most indispensable entity in the school. Their finding was on the fact that the teacher is the greatest aid to learning. Consequently, school supervision is aimed at supporting the work teachers do in the school system. Teachers as human resource in education were also studied by Ojebiyi and Adediran (2013). They linked quality and effective

educational system service delivery through the classroom teacher whose performance is subjected to monitoring and evaluation by the Ministry of Education. They found that it is the staffs who deliver the service, and that it is through a new emphasis on staff management that a customer service and performance oriented culture will gradually evolve.

The study by Onele (2014) on human resource management in secondary schools as a strategic tool for job creation in Ebonyi State, Nigeria revealed that human resource covers staff and students. He designed the descriptive survey to investigate the problem using two research questions and two hypotheses. He generated data from 232 principals of the public school in the state. He however sampled 47 principals representing 30% of the research respondents from three educational zones through the proportionate simple random sampling technique. The questionnaire was the main instrument of data collection containing 12 items and was further subjected to analysis of the mean scores and t-test statistics. The result found that staff development programme in capacity building will help greatly for employment creation in the state. The indication from this study is that human resource efficiency in the school system will demand capacity building through monitoring and evaluation in order to discover training needs of staff, particularly teachers who drive the school programme for quality secondary education in the country.

Oyekan, Adelodun and Oresajo (2015) examined the allocation of financial resources to the education industry and how it enhances productivity and students' outcomes of the secondary schools' students in the Unity College in Ogun State. The authors employ a research design involving the ex-post factor and utilized the purposive sampling technique for their study. Scholar's opinion on financial resources allocation was cited. The three Unity Federal Colleges in Ogun State utilized for the study were namely Federal government Girls Colleges, Sagamu; Federal Government College, Odagbolu and Federal Science and Technical College, Ijebu-Imushin respectively. Analysis of data generated from the respondents using percentage calculation indicated that the federal science and technical college, Ijebu-Imushin was with the high percentage of 38.08%, meaning that much productivity and students' outcomes is expected from the school. The implication of this finding is that resource allocation provides the basis for promising practices for schools. The finding aligned with the report by the Voice of Nigeria (VON) (2013), which found that the improvement in funding is geared towards improving on the standard of education provided for the citizens especially in secondary schools. Okoroma (2013) on his part discussed that there is a strong relationship between adequate funding and adequate school facilities in a study that investigated the role of instructional supervision and the continued poor performance of secondary school students in Nigeria. The author's observation is exemplified in the dismal school certificate results, complaints in local and national newspapers as well as electronic media which questioned the effectiveness of teachers in the teaching and learning process. This study above suggests that educational resources have to be available for use in order to experience optimal performance of school personnel.

3. Utilization of Educational Resources

In the context of this study, education resources consists of human, material and finance for use in the execution of programme in the school system. The use of available human, material and finance is the responsibility of school administrators. The efficient and effective use of the available resource seems to determine the extent to which educational resources will influence quality secondary education in the study area. Observation from other studies established the fact that education resources are not sufficiently supplied; but the concern of stakeholders indicates that there appears to be mismanagement of the scarce resources available to most school in the country. It is this concern that is prompting this further investigation. Studies in this regard seem to combine the variables of availability and utilization of educational resources in their discussions. In addition, majority of the study in literature assessed utilization of materials more than the other two categories of human and finance respectively.

Okeke and Okoye (2013) study the effective resource utilization in case study involving a better approach to teaching and learning of physics. According to the authors, for effective understanding of physics concepts, the application and effective use of resources is shown as a better approach. They found that the resources if well utilized, increase the achievement level of the students and also engender positive changes. The finding revealed that human and materials inputs are necessary for achieving the objectives of concepts to be

taught. This is because, material is the sum total of everything used including human and money directly or indirectly for the purpose of educational training to facilitate or encourage the acquisition of knowledge competence, skills and know-how. Similarly, the authors discovered four constraints and challenges to effective resource utilization. The lists consists of time allocation on the time-table, poor staffing, inadequate power supply and lack of opportunities for in-service training/refresher course for serving physics teachers. It was their belief that each and these entire factors act as constraint to utilization of educational resources especially as it affect instructional resource materials in the classroom.

Olelewe, Nzeadibe and Nzeadibe (2014) focus on the availability and utilization of educational resources in selected rural communities in Enugu State. The study was to track the implication for actualization of millennium development goal No. 2 in Nigeria. The investigation was founded on the observed problem which is the level of educational resources provided for the implementation of educational programmes is inadequate and irregular. This inadequacy is compounded by the meager budgetary allocation for education which has been steadily declining over the past few decades. In order to determine the assumptions, the authors stated three research questions to guide the investigation. 118 primary school in four local government area were used during a focus group discussion along other research instruments for data collection. The simple descriptive methods and the univariate summary statistics with the aid of table and graphical formats were employed; while findings shows adequate staff available for UBE implementation, there was gross inadequacy of material resources. This implies that the quality of education given to pupils in the study areas will be negatively affected. The study revealed that functional literacy will continue to elude us without some level of relevant resource available. Hence, the author believed that it will be extremely difficult for Nigeria to achieve the universal primary education component of millennium development goals (MDGs) no 2 without the provision of adequate resources. It means that even though material resources are available, their utilization in terms of their selection and appropriate use is very important.

Okemakinde, Adedeji and Ssempebwa (2015) examined the variations in the resources allocated to the technical colleges in Oyo State and the relationship between the availability and utilization of resources and academic performance in the colleges. The problem of the study was that over the last two decades, the debate on technical education has centered on such issues as access to, the quality of, funding of and benefits of technical education. Hitherto, however, questions relating to the factors accounting for the differences in the resources allocated to them; and relationship between, on one hand, the availability and utilization of resources and academic performance in technical colleges in Oyo State, Nigeria, on the other, have remained unanswered. It is this notion that drives the research. Data used for the investigation consists of documentary analysis, questionnaire and observation. Analysis of variance in the resources allocated to the colleges indicated that there was variation in the resources allocated to the colleges. Also, findings shows that all the colleges studied were under-facilitated and correlation of variable confirmed that there is relationship between the availability and utilization of resources and academic performance in the colleges. Thus, optimal utilization of resources was highly recommended. It also demand that measures for monitoring utilization of material resources in the school may provide a form of remediation. The study by Wanyangu (2017) agreed with the result stating that there was need for more efficient utilization of educational resources if student's performance was to be improved significantly. He recommends that because of lack of essential resources, inputs in many of the school, the government and parents must significantly increase school resources. In order to ascertain appropriateness of educational resources, the available resources are subjected to evaluation of school supervision to establish their suitability for use.

4. Measures of Quality Secondary Education

Nigeria deserves quality secondary education. The importance of secondary education is hinge to economic growth and human capital development. Therefore, this level of education cannot be neglected in all its ramifications. Education generally is the bedrock to development. It has been described as such by many scholars, including Kayode and Adagba (2014). According to the authors, "no nation can develop beyond its educational standards or level". They describe education as a catalyst for socio-economic and political development of a nation. They found that developed countries of the world like China, Japan, Russia and United States of American among others have achieve various breakthroughs due to their commitment to ensuring a

functional educational system in their countries. This implies that bedrock to development is founded on education of which secondary education is an essential and integral whole. In most jurisdictions, secondary education in places like the United States refers to the last four years of statutory formal education (grade nine through grade twelve) either at high school or split between a final year of junior high school and three in high school.

Abayomi, Youdeowei and Uwandu (2016) describe education as a great instrument for social, political and economic development of a nation. According to them, they see education having the ability to liberate a man and equip him to take place of pride in national development. This means that the strength, security and well being of Nigeria rest squarely on the quality of education provided for the citizens. They believe that education will continue to be great assets to many as well as a steady source of manpower supply for the state and national economy. Thus, the imperative of education that will lead to individual preparation and makes him or her contribute meaningfully to society will depend on the quality of the education provided by the government to society. Hence, education is often directed to examining variables that defines quality of education. It is the vision of the Federal Ministry of Education to provide access to quality basic and secondary education that will ensure self-reliance, preparedness for further education, good citizenship and effective participation in democratic governance.

The acquisition of quality secondary education is based on a number of factors. Ojedokun and Aladejana (2012) found a decline in quality of secondary education in Nigeria. They found out that the decline in quality is associated with the neglect of what makes education of high standard. Ochuba (2009) attempts a distinction between standard and quality as follows, that while standard is the input, and quality on the other hand implies the output. In order words, it is standard that determines quality of education. This is because standard according to Bartlett (2001) may be what is provided in the form of teaching syllabus or put precisely, the curriculum, with which the learners interact under the auspices of the teacher.

Hence, the study by Ojedokun et al (2012) indicated that the quality of curriculum inputs are indexes of content standards, the processes and conditions in school system aggregate opportunity standards while students outcomes whether good or bad will indicate performance standard. Therefore, in order to actualize and make secondary education of high standard, the curriculum must be challenging enough, by relating what is taught and learnt to the needs of the learners as well as the nation, sufficient funds or grant are made available by government to secondary schools so as to meet day-to-day obligations; the supply of qualified teachers to handle all secondary school subjects; for the purpose of effective management of class size, a normal teacher-student ratio is important. This will also ensure the achievement of effectiveness of instruction; the need for adequate physical infrastructures to cater for all curricular and co-curricular activities cannot be overstressed; functional measures for quality control is put in place to ensure that the system works as expected and amongst other factors leading to quality education.

The index of the quality of secondary education according to Ochuba (2009) is measured by students' learning outcomes, whether good or bad, meaning that results are used as indicators for performance standards, which could be regarded as indexes of output or quality of education. Ojedokun et al shows that in the Nigerian educational contexts, the results of an end of school, course or programme evaluation is often used to determine the success or quality of an educational system. The responsibility of the evaluation in a standardized examination is organized by external examination bodies such as the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) and the National Examination Council (NECO). These bodies conduct certificate examinations for senior secondary school students. Consequently, the results released at the end of the day are used to make decisions and overall evaluation of the success which helps to ascertain the level of quality of the education for the period under review. Thus, researchers based their survey on the extent to which the quality is persistently and consistently consistent. Recent studies have reviewed the evidence of the quality of secondary education in Nigeria.

Adepoju and Oluchukwu (2011) assessed and investigated the academic performance of secondary school students in two principal subjects – English Language and Mathematics at the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) in ten secondary schools typical of urban and rural locations in five randomized local

government areas of Oyo State, Nigeria between 2005 and 2007. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. An instrument titled; “Students Academic Performance in English Language and Mathematics Questionnaire (SAPEMQ) was used to collect relevant data for the study. The ten secondary schools involved based on simple random sampling technique and the statistical tools employed to analyze the data collected were percentages, mean scores and multiple regression. Four research questions and one hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. The result among other things revealed that there was a marked difference in the performance of students at the SSCE with impressive means scores at 69.8, 54.4 and 60.2 in 2005 and 2007 respectively. This results shows that there was a marginal quality of secondary education for the year under review.

5. Conclusion

The study is on the utilization of educational resources as a factor influencing quality secondary education in South-South, Nigeria. The study is premised on the belief that school personnel are not employing and using the educational resources in their teaching learning process at the secondary school level. Hence, this study looks at how the proper utilization of educational resources can spur quality education. Based on this, the paper concluded that educational resources is an integral component of the school that requires regular and prompt supervision with a bid to sustain quality in the education sector in the area under review.

6. Suggestions

Arising from the conclusion, the paper suggested that secondary school administrators and Chief inspectors of schools should consistently and regularly supervise school to ensure appropriate utilization of educational resources provided by government. The judicious use of the supplied resources will reduce the mismanagement of the available educational resources to promote quality secondary education.

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